

Mechanical Behavior of Hydrolyzed Tricalcium Phosphate/ Poly(L-lactide) composites under Various Loading Rates

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SUMMARY

Effects of strain rate on the mechanical properties of bioabsorbable tricalcium phosphate / Poly(L-lactide) composites after immersion into simulated body environments were investigated. Tensile strength decreased after 8 weeks immersion, and then kept constant. And tensile strength increased with increasing strain rate. Strain rate dependency became larger with immersion period.

Keywords: Bioabsorbable Composites, Tricalcium Phosphates, Poly(L-Lactic Acid)

INTRODUCTION

Metallic bone fixations require re-operation because of bone absorption caused by stress shielding and inflammatory. In order to improve the QOL of patients, bioresorbable bone fixations with no requirement of re-operation have been developed. Poly(L-lactide), PLLA, have been used for this fixations. PLLA is bioresorbable plastics and polymer of L-lactide within the living body. In order to improve the mechanical properties, bioactive ceramics, such as hydroxyapatite (HA) or tricalcium phosphate (TCP), /PLLA composites are developed. In the previous studies, experimental characterizations of *in vitro/in vivo* mechanical properties and bio-resorbability have been conducted on HA/PLLA and TCP/PLLA composites [1-7]. These studies are conducted at strain rate of less than 10^{-4} /s. Considering practical usage, up to strain rate of 10^1 /s and the strain rate dependency of polymer materials, characterization at higher strain rate is necessary. The objective of the present study is to clarify the effect of strain rate on the mechanical behavior of hydrolyzed TCP/PLLA composites towards material design for bioresorbable therapeutic materials considering strain rate effect.

EXPERIMENTS

Tricalcium Phosphate (TCP) powder and poly(L-lactide) (PLLA) pellet were used in preparation of TCP/PLLA composites. TCP/PLLA composites were prepared using an injection molding machine. Before injection molding, TCP and PLLA were dry mixed at weight ratio of 10.5:190, 21:180 and 32:170 (5 wt%, 10 wt%, 15 wt%) in a polyethylene bottle. The mixture was put in the hopper of the injection molding machine, and molded into rectangular-shape specimens. The geometry of the specimen was 100mm×10mm×4mm.

Immersion tests into simulated body environment were also conducted with phosphate buffered solution of pH=7.4 at 37°C in an incubator. After 8, 16 and 24 weeks, tensile tests were conducted on the specimens.

Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature using a universal testing machine and an electro-hydraulic high-speed material tensile test system at testing rate 1-1000 mm/min and 0.1- 1 m/s, respectively. After the tensile tests, the fracture surfaces of the specimens were observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows tensile Young's modulus and strength as a function of strain rate. Young's modulus kept constant up to strain rate of 10^{-1} /s for each specimen, and then increased with increasing strain rate. Tensile strength of 5 and 10wt% specimens increased with increasing strain rate up to 10^{-1} /s, and then kept constant. No dependency on strain rate was observed in 15wt% specimens.

Figure 2 shows the stress-strain curve of each specimen. In 5wt% specimens, larger fracture strain and associated ductile behavior were observed up to strain rate of 10^{-1} /s. In 10wt% specimens, lower fracture strain and failure around yielding point were observed at strain rate of 10^{-3} and 10^{-2} /s. At more than 10^{-1} /s, specimen failed before yielding. In 15wt% specimen, low fracture strain and brittle behavior were observed at all strain rates. These results suggest that increasing both TCP contents and strain rate causes decrease in fracture strain.

Figure 3 shows the fracture surface of 10wt% specimen. Two types of regions were observed at lower strain rate. That is, ductile and brittle regions. In ductile region, debondings between TCP particle and matrix grew into the void shape, especially at weak interface. These microscopic damages result in decrease in modulus and associated nonlinear stress-strain behavior. Final fracture occurred in a catastrophic manner without void formation. The number of voids decreased with increasing strain rate. This causes the suppression of nonlinear stress strain behavior, where suppression of nonlinear stress strain behavior is considered to increase the tensile strength. In the same way, the increase in brittle region decrease the fracture strain.

Figure 1 Young's modulus and strength of TCP/PLLA composites as a function of strain rate.

Figure 2 Stress-strain curve of TCPIPLLA composite under various strain rate.

Figure 3 Fracture surface of 10wt% specimen observed using a scanning electron microscope.

Figure 4 shows tensile Young's modulus as a function of strain rate after immersion test into simulated body environment. In 5 and 10wt% specimens, little decrease in modulus was observed. On the other hand, modulus decreased in 15wt% immersion specimen. No strain rate dependency was also observed in immersion specimens.

Figure 5 shows tensile strength as a function of strain rate after immersion test into simulated body environment. Tensile strength decreased after 8 weeks immersion, and then kept constant. Tensile strength of immersion specimen also increased with increasing strain rate, similar to non-immersion specimen. Strain rate dependency became larger with immersion period.

Figure 6 shows the stress-strain curves at strain rate of 10^{-1} /s. In 10 and 15 wt % specimens, fracture strain increased at 8 and 16 weeks immersion. This causes the increase in tensile strength.

(a) 5wt%

(b) 10wt%

(c) 15wt%

Figure 4 Effect of strain rate on the Young's modulus of hydrolyzed TCP/PLLA Composites.

(a) 5wt%

(b) 10wt%

(c) 15wt%

Figure 5 Effect of strain rate on the tensile strength of hydrolyzed TCP/PLLA Composites.

Figure 6 Stress-strain curve of hydrolyzed TCP/PLLA composite under strain rate of 10^1 /s.

Figure 7 shows fracture surface of 15wt% specimen. After immersion, many voids are observed comparing non-immersion specimen. Furthermore, voids also observed in brittle region of fracture surface. Voids formation makes ductile fracture and results in larger fracture strain. This is due to the decrease in interfacial strength between TCP/PLLA. Voids were also observed in brittle region. This is due to the hydrolysis of TCP particles and/or interface.

Figure 7 Fracture surface of hydrolyzed 15wt% specimen observed using a scanning electron microscope.

CONCLUSION

Young's modulus increased with increasing TCP contents, while tensile strength decreased with increasing TCP contents. The composites exhibited that the strain for nonlinear behavior initiation increased with increasing strain rates, and denoted the increase in tensile strength. In the tensile tests, modulus increased over the strain rate 10^0 /s.

From the fracture surface examination, debonding between TCP and PLLA grew into void-shape is the dominant mechanism of the composites in the early stage of the fracture. Debondings decreased with increasing strain rate, and fracture morphology became brittle.

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